

Project Title	UKRI transforming food system: Study five - Food Lives Exhibition
Status	Returned for revision
Email	E.Swan@sussex.ac.uk
Phone No.	
Applicant Status	Staff (Senior Lecturer in Human Resources and Organisational Behaviour)
Department	Management
Project Start Date	08-May-2022
Project End Date	01-Aug-2026
External Funding in place	Yes
External Collaborators	Yes
Funder/Project Title	Bbsrc-Biotechnology & Biological Sciences Research Council - Co-production of healthy, sustainable food systems for disadvant
Name of Funder	Bbsrc-Biotechnology & Biological Sciences Research Council

Ethical Review Application ER/ES483/7 (continued)

Project Description

Food Lives Exhibition is a research study that is part of the broader £6M UKRI-funded research programme 'Co-production of healthy, sustainable food systems for disadvantaged communities'. This study focuses on data to be drawn from a photography exhibition and food activities event to be held June 1st 2020 in an estate in Tower Hamlets. The study encompasses a range of tried-and-tested research methods which will be mostly undertaken on the day or just after:

1. Semi structured food practices interviews
2. Food mapping (Marte, 2007)
3. Food and photography prompts
4. Participant packs (Thompson, 2012)
5. Collaborative event ethnography (Zanotti, & Suiseeya, 2020).

The aim is to provide illuminate residents' lived experience, memories, views and feelings in relation to food procurement, preparation, and consumption in their everyday lives.

The event nature of the design means that we can gather data from a range of methods and media which make the most of the one-off nature of the event; enable the research to be more participant led in that potential participants can choose which method might best suit them in relation to time/privacy/preference/literacy.

Our design raises a number of ethical issues which we are keen to work through. Underpinning our research is a feminist anti-racist methodology based on critical nutrition studies of non-stigmatisation and objectification of research participants.

This research study is part of the bigger UKRI-funded project. Dr Katerina Psarikidou and Dr Elaine Swan are the project research investigators based at the University of Sussex. Based on the principles of research co-production, the project is envisioned to provide citizens of socio-culturally diverse communities with choice and agency over the food they consume, the chains through which they access their food, and the policy frameworks that are needed to support the vision of a more inclusive and socio-environmentally just agri-food system for all.

Ethical Review Form Section A (ER/ES483/7)	
Question	Response
>> Checklist	
A1. Will your study involve participants who are currently or potentially vulnerable or unable to give informed consent or in a dependent position (e.g. people under 18, people with learning difficulties, over-researched groups or people in care facilities)?	No
A2. Will participants be required to take part in the study without their consent or knowledge at the time (e.g. covert observation of people in non-public places), and / or will deception of any sort be used? Please refer to the British Psychological Society Code of Ethics and Conduct (or similar guidelines) for further information.	No
A3. Unless specifically and clearly consented (e.g. a media release form), will it be possible, through a research output, to identify participants in any way? (This does not include taking email details for participant prize draws or identifying participants from signed consent forms or holding identity encryption spreadsheets that are stored securely separate from the research data).	No
A4. Might the study induce psychological stress or anxiety, or produce humiliation or cause harm or negative consequences beyond the risks likely to be encountered in the everyday life of the participants?	Yes
A5. Is there a risk that the research topic might lead to disclosures from the participant concerning their beliefs, involvement in illegal actions or any other activities that may represent a threat to themselves or others?	No
A6. Will the study involve collecting any personal special category information* in a form that could allow the participant/ participants to be identified? [* identifiers relating to race, ethnic origin, politics, religion, trade union membership, philosophical beliefs, genetics, biometrics, health, sex life or sexual orientation]	Yes
A7. Will any drugs, placebos or other substances (such as food substances or vitamins) be administered as part of this study and will any invasive or potentially harmful procedures of any kind will be used?	No
A8. Will your project involve working with any substances and / or equipment which may be considered hazardous?	No
A9. Will your study involve the taking and/or storage of human tissue that falls under the Human Tissue Act (HTA)? http://www.sussex.ac.uk/staff/research/governance/erp_overview/humantissue	No
>> Risk Assessment	
A10. If you have answered Yes to ANY of the above questions, your application may be considered as HIGH risk. If, however you wish to make a case that your application should be considered as LOW risk please enter the reasons here. Researchers should note that SREOs or C-RECs may decide NOT to agree with the case that you have made.	

Ethical Review Form Section C (ER/ES483/7)	
Question	Response
>> Risk Checklist - Participants	
C1. Is DBS (Disclosure and Barring Service) clearance necessary for this project? If yes, please ensure you complete Section C24a below	No
C2. Are alcoholic drinks, drugs, placebos or other substances (such as food substances or vitamins) to be administered to the study participants?	Yes
C3. Can you think of anything else that might be potentially harmful to participants in this research?	
C4. Does the project involve working with any substances and/or equipment which may be considered hazardous? (Please refer to the University's Control of Hazardous Substances Policy http://www.sussex.ac.uk/hso/policies).	No
C5. Could the nature or subject of the research potentially have an emotionally disturbing impact on the researcher(s)?	Yes
C5a. If yes, briefly describe what measures will be taken to help the researcher(s) to manage this.	<p>There is potential for participants to experience some anxiety or stress about their food practices and understandings through the course of the research. The researchers are aware of the importance of maintaining boundaries with participants, for the wellbeing of both parties. By employing a participant led structure in methods, the researcher will encourage participants to raise themes that are of importance in their own lives, making it clear that activities can stop or be redirected at any time. Given the existing relationship with WEN , all participants will be directed towards appropriate support services, should anything arise within interviews that may be distressing for participants. This includes but is not limited to: Access to emergency food provision; support with eating disorders and support with mental illness. The researchers and local gatekeepers are aware of organisations which could provide further help should signposting be required.</p> <p>In terms of the observations, we will ensure we respect privacy and are not invasive in our observations. We will have posters around the estate explaining our method and that people can request to be excluded from our photos and notes.</p>
C6. Could the nature or subject of the research potentially expose the researcher(s) to threats of physical violence and / or verbal abuse?	No
C6a. If yes, briefly describe what measures will be taken to mitigate this.	
C7. Does the research involve any fieldwork - Overseas or in the UK?	Yes

<p>C7a. If yes, where will the fieldwork take place? (All research requiring overseas travel will require the submission of a fully completed OTTSRA form). In the event that the Foreign and Commonwealth Office has travel warnings in place for the country (ies) to be visited you will also need to provide a detailed risk assessment.</p>	<p>St Georges Estate, Shadwell, London E1</p>
<p>C8. Will any researchers be in a lone working situation?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>C8a. If yes, briefly describe the location, time of day and duration of lone working. What precautionary measures will be taken to ensure safety of the researcher(s)?</p>	
<p>C9. Can you think of anything else that might be potentially harmful to the researcher(s) in this research?</p>	
<p>>> Data Collection and Analysis (Please provide full details)</p>	
<p>C10. PARTICIPANTS: How many people do you envisage will participate, who are they, and how will they be selected?</p>	<p>1. Semi structured food practices interviews - 10 2. Food mapping (Marte, 2007) - 5 3. Food and photography prompts - 15 4. Participant packs (Thompson, 2012) which contain a food diaries and food mapping brief - 10 5. Collaborative event ethnography (Zanotti, & Suiseeya, 2020) - observation of between 20-80 people Apart from method 5, participants will be invited to participate on the day. They will be provided with invitation about the research methods via postcards delivered to each residents, posters on the estate and more information on the project website based on information sheets and consent principles. On the day, people interested will be given information sheets and verbal briefings. The participant packs will contain information sheets and consent forms and will be briefed at the event. Posters around the estate at the event will explain the research, the researchers presence and their observations. We will offer a verbal consent process to those who prefer that. Participants will be selected on the basis that they consent, and that they are able to contribute to the methods usefully.</p>

<p>C11. RECRUITMENT: How will participants be approached and recruited?</p>	<p>Participants will be approached first by postcards through their doors and posters on the estate. This will be backed up with information available through a link on the project website. People will be recruited via verbal and printed information on the day on the basis of their residency on the estate and ability to meet the requirements of the research and their giving of consent. Consent won't be given for for the event ethnography.</p> <p>On meeting with each participant, we will brief on the ethical process, re-provide information sheets and informed consent forms or where necessary due to technology or language skills, a verbal consent. The participants will have the opportunity to raise any questions about the project. They can decide which methods they would like to participate in.</p> <p>If they choose to take a participant pack for later they can take part in the research at their own convenience. Participants will receive a shopping voucher as recompense/remuneration for their participation in the research. The precise amount will depend on which methods the participants undertake but likely to be 5-15 pounds per method. There will not be time for participants to undertake more than one method at the event. The pack will contain 2-3 activities - food mapping, food diaries and food memories and again depending on which ones are completed, suitable token of a voucher will be offered.</p>
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C12. METHOD: What research method(s) do you plan to use; e.g. interview, questionnaire/self-completion questionnaire, field observation, audio/audio-visual recording etc.?

1. Semi structured food practices interviews - see suggested questions. We will have researcher tables around the estate where participants can approach us if they'd like to take part in any of our methods.

These will take place in the grounds of the estate. We are setting up tables with chairs where people can learn about the methods, and volunteer to undertake one of them if they choose to. The interview tables will be placed across the estate so there is some privacy. We are also offering a walk and talk option as one of the goals is to encourage people to visit different parts of the estate like the allotments and orchard.

2. Food mapping (Marte, 2007)

Food maps include: routes of food shopping journeys in neighbourhoods; ; a sketch of their staple food, its ingredients, and where they are sourced;

3. Food and photography prompts

There will be large posters around the estate and different food related prompts or questions. Participants can write in their own notebooks and hand them in to us, after our briefing. Or they can come and talk to us about their responses.

4. Participant packs (Thompson, 2012)

These will be small packs of activities - food mapping, food diaries and food memories - participants can decide which they would like to do and we will have a special table with two researchers briefing them on the packs. The packs will include informed consent and information sheets.

The packs were designed as a set of resources for participants and as a point of reference. They will consist of a title sheet (with our contact details restated); a reproduction of the information sheet ; illustrated instructions for the photovoice exercise; illustrated instructions and templates to follow; a smaller contract information card to pass on to other potential participants; and a note sheet on which participants could manually record their food and drink (if they so wishes). Participants will be invited to carry out the photo diary for a four-day period consistent with the literature. We will provide a clear set of illustrated instructions and examples was a way of supporting the most participant-led stage of data collection.

At the briefing sessions we will explain the duration and requirements of the study. We also have Sylheti speakers for older Bangladeshi potential participants.

5. Collaborative event ethnography including audio-visual recordings and observation (Zanotti, & Suiseeya, 2020).

The researchers will also take field notes, and photographs of residents at the event, their responses to the photos, food, activities and research methods Observations that will form part of the analysis. We will have posters up around the estate explaining what we are doing and that if they don't want us to take their photo or observe us to come and tell one of us. We will avoid taking photos of children.

C13. LOCATION: Where will the project be carried out e.g. public place, in researcher's office, in private office at organisation?	The research will be carried out in the grounds of the estate.
>> Ethical Considerations (Please provide full details)	

C14. PARTICIPANT WELLBEING: Will the study involve engaging participants in the discussion of distressing or sensitive topics? (e.g. sexual activity, drug use, ethnicity, political behaviour, potentially illegal activities). If so, please set out how you will manage the well-being of participants.

There is potential for participants to experience some anxiety or stress about their food practices and understandings through the course of the research. The researchers are aware of the importance of maintaining boundaries with participants, for the wellbeing of both parties. By employing a participant led structure in the methods, the researcher will encourage participants to raise themes that are of importance in their own lives, making it clear that activities can stop or be redirected at any time. Given the existing relationship with WEN, all participants will be directed towards appropriate support services, should anything arise within interviews, mapping and other methods that may be distressing for participants. This includes but is not limited to: Access to emergency food provision; support with eating disorders and support with mental illness. The researchers and local gatekeepers are aware of organisations which could provide further help should signposting be required.

Examples include

For Tower Hamlets, mental health:

Mind in Tower Hamlets and Newham is a community mental health charity that provides advice and support to anyone with a mental health or emotional issue. They also provide free counselling for Tower Hamlets residents.

Contact: 020 7510 4247/4248 or email info@mithn.org.uk.

Inspire Mental Health Consortium delivers new mental health, recovery and wellbeing services, to improve the outcomes and life chances for people living with mental health problems in Tower Hamlets.

Contact: 0330 053 8122 or email enquiry@inspire-wellbeing.org.uk.

Food relief organisations in Tower Hamlets: the link provides access to a range of food relief and poverty resources that could be given to participants depending on their needs
<https://www.wen.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/Food-in-Tower-Hamlets-April-2021.pdf>

<p>C15. INFORMED CONSENT: Please describe the process you will use to ensure your participants are freely giving fully informed consent to participate. This will usually include the provision of an Information Sheet and will normally require a Consent Form unless there is justification for not doing so. (Please state this clearly).</p>	<p>For all the methods, except the event ethnography, participants will be encouraged to give their informed consent through</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Information about the project and consent processes to be circulated via a postcard with links to our website. 2. Provision of information sheets and oral consent agreements/consent forms. 3. Ensuring that the researchers brief the consent process clearly before our methods are undertaken. We have two researchers who speak Sylheti the main other language used on the estate apart from English. 4. We will ensure that participants can ask questions and understand what will happen to their data.
<p>C16. RIGHT OF WITHDRAWAL: Participants should be able to withdraw from the research at any time. Participants should also be able to withdraw their data if it is linked to them and should be told when this will no longer be possible (e.g. once it has been included in the final report). Please describe the exact arrangements for withdrawal from participation and withdrawal of data for your study.</p>	<p>Participants will be able to withdraw at any point within the workshop themselves, without having to provide any explanation. They may request withdrawal of their data by 1st September 2022 which is the start of our planned data analysis.</p>
<p>C17. OTHER ETHICAL ISSUES: If you answered YES to anything in A.1 above (participants who are potentially vulnerable or unable to give informed consent or in a dependent position) you must specifically address this here. Please also consider whether there are other ethical issues you should be covering here. Please also refer to the professional code of conduct you intend to follow in your research.</p>	<p>The event ethnography will involve filming and observations. We will have posters around the estate explaining this. We will have a table where people can ask about this aspect of the research and make it clear that people can ask not to be filmed. We will avoid as much as possible filming children. We will only use the film for our analytic purposes.</p> <p>As sociologists, we generally follow the BSA code https://www.britsoc.co.uk/media/24310/bsa_statement_of_ethical_practice.pdf</p> <p>But their guidance on observations is limited and so we will follow the SRA code - see here https://the-sra.org.uk/common/Uploaded%20files/ethical%20guidelines%202003.pdf</p>
<p>>> Data Protection, Confidentiality, and Records Management</p>	
<p>C18. DPA: Will you ensure that the processing of personal information related to the study will be in full compliance with the Data Protection Act 2018 (GDPR)? Please give full details under C19a. http://www.sussex.ac.uk/ogs/policies/information/dpa</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>C18a. C18a. If you are transferring any personal data outside of the United Kingdom, you must explain how you will comply with data protection legislation. Further guidance is available at: https://www.sussex.ac.uk/ogs/policies/information/dpa/transfersoutside</p>	

<p>C19. CONFIDENTIALITY: Will you take steps to ensure the confidentiality of personal information? Please explain how any identifiable personal records and research data will be managed and stored whilst ensuring that participants have given appropriate informed consent for this in C19a and or C20 below.</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>C19a. DATA MANAGEMENT: Please provide details of any anonymisation procedures and of physical and technical security measures (including secure storage) of identifiable personal and research data here. Indicate how these will be employed in the collection, analysis and research output and dissemination stages.</p>	<p>The names of all participants in the study will be anonymised in order to protect their identities although the limitations of this will be discussed with them given that photographs and recordings could lead to identifications. All data will be managed by the researcher and securely stored and transferred using OneDrive. Project passwords will be pre-set and will contain a combination of at least eight alphanumeric and symbolic characters. Once uploaded to OneDrive, original copies of data will be securely deleted from local storage locations. The shared project workspace on OneDrive will be maintained, organised and updated by the researcher, who will do weekly checks on version control, archiving, monitoring and tidying. All raw data files will be named with anonymous unique IDs and a password-protected database will keep record of links between unique IDs and personal data. Shared folders containing raw data will have access limited to the research team.</p>
<p>C20. CONSENT: If personal information related to this study will be retained and shared (i.e. in outputs) in a form that is not fully anonymised (separated from information that can identify the participant) please outline how participants will be made aware of this (including any limitations) and indicate their consent.</p>	
<p>C21. Will the Principal Investigator take full responsibility during the study, for ensuring appropriate storage and security of information (including research data, consent forms and administrative records) and, where appropriate, will the necessary arrangements be made in order to process copyright material lawfully?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>C21a. If you answered "No" to the above question, please give further details of how data and records will be managed:</p>	
<p>C22. Who will have access to personal information and data relating to this study?</p>	<p>The research team at Sussex which includes academics and a project manager.</p>
<p>C23. DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN: AFTER the study: State how long study information including research data, consent forms and personal identification will be retained, in what format(s) and where the information will be kept. http://www.sussex.ac.uk/ogs/policies/information/recordsmanagementguidance</p>	<p>The data will be deposited in the University of Sussex Research Data Repository (USRDR) Figshare, where it will be preserved for at least 10 years post-project in line with the Concordat on Open Research Data (2016) and to allow for maximum project exposure and impact. Participants will be notified in the participant information that their data will be securely stored in accordance with GDPR requirements and will only be presented anonymously.</p>
<p>>> Other Ethical Clearances and Permissions</p>	
<p>C24. Are any other ethical clearances or permissions (internal or external) required? Please see the help text (i) for further details.</p>	<p>No</p>

C24a. If yes, please give further details including the name and address of the organisation. If other ethical approval has already been received please attach evidence of approval, otherwise you will need to supply it when ready. (You do not need to provide evidence of a current DBS check at this point).

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

Study title: Food Lives: Exploring household and community food practices

INVITATION

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide whether to take part, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully.

WHAT IS THE PURPOSE OF THE STUDY?

The purpose of this study is to understand more about peoples' food practices in the home and neighbourhood.

WHY HAVE I BEEN INVITED TO PARTICIPATE?

You have been invited to participate because you are an adult resident of London Borough of Tower Hamlets. We are interested in people's understandings of food. We think you will have ideas and experiences which are important for researchers and policy makers to understand.

DO I HAVE TO TAKE PART?

No! It is up to you to decide whether to take part. If you do decide to take part, you will be given this information sheet to keep and will be asked to sign a consent form. You are however still free to withdraw at any time and without giving a reason.

WHAT WILL HAPPEN TO ME IF I TAKE PART?

You will take part in one or two of the following activities:

- *Food mapping* – mapping your food shopping journeys with a researcher
- *A short interview* – discussing your food shopping and cooking with a researcher
- *Food prompts* – complete a range of short activities displayed around the exhibition trail
- *Participant packs* – complete a food diary including taking photographs after the exhibition
- *Instagram* – upload photographs about the exhibition during or after the event

Participants will receive a small recompense in the form of a shopping voucher for their time.

The interview will take place on the estate at one of the tables or as a walk and talk around the orchard and grounds, depending on what you prefer.

WHAT ARE THE POSSIBLE DISADVANTAGES AND RISKS OF TAKING PART?

The primary disadvantage of participating in this study is the time taken to participate. Participating in the research is not anticipated to cause you any discomfort. The potential physical and/or psychological harm or distress that can be generated by discussing food will be kept to the minimum through the activities chosen, and the experience of the researchers. Dr Elaine Swan has received training in counselling skills and the researchers are experienced in qualitative research about food. By employing exploratory research methods and an open structure to the discussions, the researcher will encourage participants to raise themes that are of importance in their own lives, making it clear that activities can stop or be redirected at any time.

WHAT ARE THE POSSIBLE BENEFITS OF TAKING PART?

By taking part in this study, you are helping to expand knowledge on food practices in your neighbourhood and council area which can potentially influence future food-related policies. This data will be of potential benefit in informing the agendas of organisations concerned with food distribution within the area.

WILL MY INFORMATION IN THIS STUDY BE KEPT CONFIDENTIAL?

All information collected about you will be kept strictly confidential. Confidentiality, privacy, and anonymity will be ensured through strict adherence to the guidelines for storing, managing and processing data set out in the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the UK Data Protection Act 2018.

After the undertaking the research methods, only the researchers will have access to your data. We will keep all personal information about you (e.g., your name and other information about you that can identify you) confidential, that is we will not share it with others. We will also anonymise the written transcript produced by the transcriber. This means that we will remove any personal information.

All audio-visual data collected will be downloaded and stored securely on a University of Sussex managed storing system, named OneDrive.

WHAT SHOULD I DO IF I WANT TO TAKE PART?

To opt in for the study, please agree to take part by signing the consent form or agreeing to the oral consent.

WHAT WILL HAPPEN TO THE RESULTS OF THE RESEARCH STUDY?

The results of this research study will be used to inform several academic pieces of work. These may include: articles in published academic journals, academic book chapters, public presentations, conferences and/or events. Copies of any research output will be made freely available to all participants, although participants should note that this process is planned to take place over a 4-year period, with data retained for the length of that period. When writing up the findings from this study, we would like to reproduce some of the views and ideas you shared with us. We will only use anonymised quotes so that although we will use your exact words, we will do our best to ensure you cannot be identified in the publications, although we cannot guarantee this.

WHO IS ORGANISING AND FUNDING THE RESEARCH?

Research will be undertaken by members of the Management Department and Science Policy Research Unit (SPRU) at the University of Sussex. The project is part of a part of a study funded by the government agency, UK Research and Innovation "UKRI", entitled 'Transforming Food Systems for Disadvantaged Communities', which is administered at the University of Reading.

WHO HAS APPROVED THIS STUDY?

The study has been improved by the Social Sciences & Arts Cross-Schools Research Ethics Committee (SSARTA) at the University of Sussex. The ethical review application numbers is ER/ES483/7.

CONTACT FOR FURTHER INFORMATION

If you require any additional information, please contact Dr Elaine Swan by emailing e.swan@sussex.ac.uk.

If you have any questions or concerns relating to this research please contact Ruth Stirton, Chair of the Social Sciences and Arts Cross Schools Research Ethics Committee (r.stirton@sussex.ac.uk).

INSURANCE

The University of Sussex has insurance in place to cover its legal liabilities in respect of this study.

Thank you for taking the time to read this information sheet. Any participation is greatly appreciated.

Indicative questions for interviews:

- What are your “staple” or most regular foods and meals?
- What ingredients do you use for this meal?
- How often do you have this meal?
- Where do you find these ingredients?
- What is your favourite ingredient to cook?
- How often do you make this meal?
- Do you like to eat it?
- What is it that you like about it?
- Do you like to prepare and cook it?
- Can you substitute other ingredients?
- Do you sometimes share this meal for any of your relatives and/or friends?
- Do you ever prepare foods together with your extended family and/or friends?
- How did you learn how to cook this meal?
- Are there any ingredients that you find difficult to get?
- Do you find any challenges with your regular food shop?

Indicative questions for map drawing exercises

- Could you draw a line showing the journey from your home to the food shops/markets/food banks that you regularly go to?
- Can you map out a regular and a special meal and the ingredients used on the map?
- Could you mark with a dot on this map of your neighbourhood your favourite food shops/markets?
- Can you map places you might get takeaway or restaurant foods? Could you mark with a dot on this map of your neighbourhood the places that you are important or special for your daily life?

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CHECKLIST: VERBAL CONSENT FROM RESEARCH PARTICIPANTS
FOR RESEARCHER USE ONLY¹

Title of Project: **Food Lives**

Name of Researcher and School: **Dr Elaine Swan, Dr Jesse Hsu, School of Management and Dr Katerina Psarikidou, SPRU**

C-REC Ref no: <Insert ER no.>

A. Process of obtaining verbal consent from research participants:

- 1) Give an account of how you will verbally **explain** to the research participants as clearly as possible and in terms that they are familiar with:
- The **aims** and **objectives** of your research;
 - The reasons why you have **selected** them for this research;
 - The reasons why their story/knowledge/understanding/opinions are **relevant** to your research;
 - The ways in which the research data will be **used**: for example, in a dissertation/thesis/publications/blogs/reports/policy documents.

Our research study, “Food Lives” explores how you do your food provisioning, shopping, preparation and cooking. We are part of a larger multi-university government-funded project on improving access to healthy food in the UK. You have been selected as a participant because you are a resident of one of the communities that we are researching. Your expertise and experience with cooking and food shopping is important to us because your knowledge can inform future food policies. The research data collected for this project may be used for: for research reports, journal publications, book chapters, conference and workshop presentations, policy documents, blog posts, and food product development

Please expand the box as necessary

- 2) I will **verbally explain** to the research participants:

- That they can **withdraw** from the research at any time without giving a reason, and without being penalised or disadvantaged in any way and/or that they can tell me not to use certain types of information at any time;
- What **confidentiality** means in the context of the research and how confidentiality will be maintained in this particular context (OR explain why confidentiality cannot be maintained in this particular case – e.g. focus group);
- What **anonymity** means and how it will be maintained in this particular context (OR I will ask approval for the use of their name/location/company/organisation in the final report/dissertation/further publication).

¹ To be submitted as supporting documentation for ethical review and approval

- 3) Describe below how you will **verbally explain** to your informants that they can **withdraw** from the research at any time, what **confidentiality** and **anonymity** mean in your research context, and how you will explain these terms to your informants:

You may choose to withdraw from our research study at any point without having to provide us a reason. There will be no penalty to do so. You may also ask us to not use any data — recorded conversation, photographs, observation notes— for the study or future research outputs such as journal articles, book chapters, conference presentations, policy reports, until September 1st 2022 when we begin our analysis. We will try to protect your anonymity but we cannot guarantee it because the photographs may contain images of objects which could potentially identify you. We will ensure written texts will not contain any identifiable features such as names, occupations, and detailed personal information unless you consent to these. Your names will be anonymised in our research databases order to protect your identity. All data collected for this project will be stored on a secure application called OneDrive which is licensed for the University of Sussex. We will have project passwords and store data on secure university storage systems. Once uploaded to OneDrive, all original data files will be deleted from researcher storage devices. All data files will be named using anonymous IDs.

- 4) I will verbally **check** with the research participants that (tick, as applicable):

- They are happy to be interviewed and/or observed by me;
- They are happy for me to be present at and/or participate in their activities;
- They are happy for me to take notes on the interview/observations/interactions;
- They are happy for the interview/observation/interaction to be:
- photographed
 - audio taped
- ***Where photographs, video or audio tape are to be shown to others, specific and separate consent should be sought in written, video or audio form.***
 - ***This consent should involve a full explanation of the kinds of contexts in which these media are to be shown.***
 - ***Media should not be published – online or elsewhere – without specific consent.***
- They are happy to be contacted again for a further interview should that be required.

- 5) I will give the research participants the opportunity to **ask any questions** about any of the above or any other concerns they may have.
- 6) I understand that seeking verbal consent will involve explaining all I have documented above and that verbal consent is an ongoing process. I understand that I will need to document the ongoing process of verbal consent.

B. Process in which verbal consent cannot be obtained:

If participant observation and/or other ethnographic research methods will be used in which verbal consent will not or cannot be sought/obtained, the following need to be considered by the researcher:

- | | |
|----|--|
| 1) | Explain why the aims and objectives of the research cannot always be fully explained to the research participants (this might differ per group/individual): |
|----|--|

	There will be times when we are observing large groups. We expect up to 100 people.
2)	Explain why confidentiality and/or anonymity cannot be explained and/or maintained:
	This will make it difficult to obtain consent.
3)	Explain why research participants cannot be asked for approval for recording and/or particular use of information:
	We will put up posters with information about our research on
4)	Explain how you ensure that negative or harmful impacts of the research on the research participants will be minimised:
	We will not invade their privacy when observing. We will enable participants to direct as much of their discussion as possible and not push any person to disclose any more than they appear to want.

C. Researcher Training and Consultation of Professional Guidelines

- 1) I confirm that in the course of my research design, I have received the following training in the ethical aspects of my research (please give details of any modules, CPD or other research ethics training you have attended in the last 18 months):

Two of us teach research methods and regularly update our teaching materials to cover debates and procedures on ethics in line with professional ethical guideline.

- 2) I confirm that I have read and carefully considered the ethical guidelines of the main professional associations for my subject area (eg: the ASA ethical guidelines: <https://www.theasa.org/ethics/guidelines.shtml>) and incorporated them into my research design.

Researcher Signature:

Date:

Notes for use

[to be removed before submission for review]

Note: This is a form that should be used as a checklist of issues to be considered before you conduct research using verbal consent. It also documents how you plan to do so and should be completed in as much detail as possible to demonstrate that you have thought through the issues fully.

As such, the form also allows the SREO or C-REC to further evaluate whether your decision to use verbal consent is appropriate.

Please remember, since reviewers may not know you personally or be familiar with your research design, providing this information helps them to understand how you plan to conduct your research.

It is **not** a form to be given to the research participants to complete or sign.

Researchers should keep in mind that sharing information with the participant and seeking consent in research serves two important and closely linked principles:

Firstly, a fundamental principle of ethical research is that **participation and consent is voluntary and informed**. Instances in which the real reason for participation is initially 'masked' from individuals (such as is employed in Psychology or other disciplines) will be subject to discipline-based conventions or conditions that will be spelled out to the reviewing Ethics Committee at review stage.

Secondly, the **processing of any personal data for research purposes is subject to the requirements** of the [Data Protection legislation](#) that researchers need to understand and follow. The legislation expects us to be fair and transparent so that participants understand how their personal data will be processed, particularly if that involves *Special Category Data*². Information about data protection in the context of research can be found on the [data protection webpages](#) and applicants can seek advice by contacting the [Data Protection Officer](#).

The consent process should usually cover the following areas:

1. The participant's understanding of the research
 2. Consent to the way in which research will be carried out
 3. Confidentiality of information (the *ethical* basis of research)
 4. Right to withdraw participation and/ or data in the study
 5. Future data re-use (when **specifically** required)
- All requests for consent should be **specific, unambiguous and informed**. All statements above that do not apply to the research should be removed. Studies that require different data types to be taken or use different media within the same project should take care that consent is *granular* whenever possible.
 - In some fields of research, it could be helpful to re-use the data for future research and analysis. If it is likely that your data is of this kind and you want to have the option to use the data for other purposes, or for it to be available to other researchers, you must obtain **explicit** permission and describe what you want the participant to agree to in the Explanatory Statement.
 - If the study involves the possible disclosure of information (either in focus groups, one to one interviews or through being passed on in any other forms of communication), the duty to pass on information that may have a bearing on the safety of others (for example in the context of possible terrorism or safeguarding concerns) will require that the participant is informed of this fact.

² Personal data relating to racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, trade union membership, the processing of genetic data, biometric data (where used for ID purposes), data concerning health, or data concerning sex life or sexual orientation.

CONSENT FORM FOR PROJECT PARTICIPANTS

Title of Project: Food Lives: Exploring household and neighbourhood food practices

Name of Researcher and School: Dr Katerina Psarikidou, SPRU, Dr Elaine Swan and Dr Jesse Hsu, School of Management

Please tick
YES NO

- | | | |
|--|--|--|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I consent to participate in the following activities with the researchers – tick as appropriate, choosing a maximum of 2: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Food maps • Interview • Participant pack | <input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> |
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I agree to allow the following to be audio-video recorded: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Food maps <input type="checkbox"/> Interview | <input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> |
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I have been briefed on the participant pack and understand that I must not take photographs of people without their consent. | <input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> |
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I consent to being informed about follow-up research activities and potential participation in future research. | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I have read the information sheet, had the opportunity to ask questions and I understand the principles, procedures and possible risks involved. | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I understand that personal data will be used for the purposes of this research study. I understand that such information will be treated strictly confidential and handled in accordance with Data Protection legislation. | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I understand that any information given by me may be used in future reports, academic articles, publications or presentations by the researcher and the project team, but my personal information will not be included and I will not be identifiable. | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I understand that data will be kept according to the university guidelines for a minimum of 10 years after the end of the study. | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I understand that my participation is voluntary, that I can choose not to participate in part or all of the project, and that I can withdraw at any stage of the project without being penalised or disadvantaged in any way. | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I understand that I can no longer request withdrawal of my data from the project after 1st September 2022. | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I agree to take part in the above University of Sussex research project | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |

Name:

Signature:

Date:

HELP US
LEARN

PHOTO
TRAIL

CHILDREN'S
ACTIVITIES

FREE
FOOD

FREE FAMILY FOOD EVENING

Join us for an evening celebrating
food and its role in local people's
lives.

1st JUNE, 4-7PM

ST GEORGE'S ESTATE

As part of the Food Lives Tower Hamlets programme, Wen and the University of Sussex are hosting an event for St George's residents. Find out about Food Lives, get involved and help us understand how you buy, cook, grow and share food. Tell us what changes you'd like to see, too. You'll get a shopping voucher as a token of thanks for taking part in the research.

WHAT'S ON

OUTDOOR FOOD PHOTO TRAIL

Featuring food photos by Tower Hamlets residents

FREE LOCALLY MADE FOOD

Enjoy delicious dishes from local chefs

FOOD PROJECTS ON THE ESTATE

Find out about our growing spaces, orchard and compost

CHILDREN'S ACTIVITIES

Competitions and activities for children of all ages

TAKE PART IN RESEARCH

Speak to our researchers or take activities home with you

SIGN UP

For future research activities like cook-alongs or interviews

FIND OUT MORE

Email Elaine at e.swan@sussex.ac.uk

Visit <https://tinyurl.com/3dbpj926>

TOWER HAMLETS FOOD SUPPORT

March 2022 update

POWERED BY
Wen.

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FOOD PROVISION

FOOD BANKS

Drop-in/Open access:

Bethnal Green and Bow Food Banks

Bethnal Green:

Wednesdays 2-7pm at Raine's Foundation School, Approach Road, E2 9LY.

Contact bethnalgreenfoodbank@gmail.com @BethnalFoodbank

Bow:

Mondays 8.30-12.30 at the Bromley by Bow Centre, E3 3BT. Entrance through the park on Bruce Road or St.Leonards Street.

Contact info@bowfoodbank.org 07934 734603 (call or text) @bowfoodbank

Neighbours in Poplar, St Matthias Community Centre, 113 Poplar High St, Poplar, E14 0AE. Open every day 10am-1pm. Walk-in service, though helpful if people call with requests for support.

Contact 020 7987 0257 @Nip_Poplar

Osmani Centre, 58 Underwood Road, London, E1 5AW. Open Wednesdays 12-3pm.

Contact 020 7247 8080 eet@osmanitrust.org

Salvation Army, Kerbey Street, E14 6AJ. Thursday 10.30-12.30.

Contact David 020 7987 9405

St Dunstan's Food Bank, Stepney High St, London E1 0NR is supporting 40 families and individuals. Open for donations and to collect food Tuesday to Friday 10am-4pm and Saturday 10am-3pm.

Contact 020 7702 8685 @DunstanST

St Luke's Food Bank, Alpha Grove, London E14 8LH. Tuesdays and Thursdays 10am-12pm. Contact 07810 748534 fuzz@stlukesmillwall.org

Weavers Food Bank COVID-19 Crisis Support Service Weavers Community Centre, 10 Shacklewell Street, Bethnal Green E2 7EG. Thursdays 2-3:30pm

Contact 020 7739 8568 info@weaversforum.org

Area-specific/registration required:

Christ Church, 151 Manchester Rd, Island Gardens, Isle of Dogs, London E14 3DR
Distributing food to vulnerable individuals in the Isle of Dogs via local volunteers.
Contact Fr Tom Pyke 02034884594

Dorset Community Association, Diss Street, London E2 7QX (for residents of Dorset Estate and Columbia Road area). Thursday 2-4pm.
Contact Nazrul 07984 966565

Ensign Youth Club, Wellclose Square(off the Highway), London E1 8HY. Collection Monday, Wednesday and Friday 10am-1pm. For residents of St Katharine area.
Contact Shafee 07949 573 730/ 020 7702 3340.

Food for Aldgate, Toynbee Hall, 28 Commercial St, London E1 6LS. Fridays 1.30-3pm. For residents of Aldgate area. Registration required.
Contact Paul paul.wilson@eastendhomes.net 07904670658

Good Shepherd Mission, 17 Three Colts Lane, Bethnal Green, E2 6JL. For individuals and families near Weavers Field in Bethnal Green/Whitechapel.
Mondays 12-2pm. Contact Darren Prince darren.prince@goodshepherdmission.org.uk OR Emily Bennett emily.bennett@goodshepherdmission.org.uk

Jesuit Refugee Service. Supports destitute Asylum Seekers who have had their initial claim for asylum refused and are not entitled to any statutory support
Contact Rhiannon 020 7488 7310, uk@jrs.net

Limehouse Project Food Hub, Burdett Road Unit 419 (Arch), London E3 4AA
Saturdays - Pick from 11am - 2pm and deliveries from 11am - 5pm.
Contact Momina Begum m.begum@limehouseproject.org.uk, 07946 391 570.

Royal Foundation St Katherine's, 2 Butcher Row, Limehouse, London E14 8DS.
Supporting a limited number of families. Contact foodbank@limehouseaid.org for more information.

St George in the East church, 16 Cannon Street Road, Shadwell, E1 0BH. Thursdays 1-3pm for people living in E1 area. Contact 07957 695993 office@stgeorgeintheeast.org

HOT MEALS (walk-in /delivery)

Methodist Church Tower Hamlets, 1 Merchant Street, London E3 4LY. FoodCycle runs a takeaway meal service every Friday 7-8pm.

Neighbours in Poplar, St Matthias Community Centre, 113 Poplar High St, Poplar, E14 0AE delivers hot meals to residents.

St John on Bethnal Green, 200 Cambridge Heath Rd, Bethnal Green, London E2 9PA 'Tuesday Night Bites' hot meal provided every Tuesday 6-7pm.

Whitechapel Mission, 212 Whitechapel Road, London E1 1BJ - serves breakfast Monday-Sunday 6-11am.

Women's Inclusive Team, Mayfield House, 202 Cambridge Heath Road, London, E2 9LJ.

Hot meal Monday to Friday. All meals are Hala. All new members should fill in an [eligibility form](#) if possible. Contact Shakila Ali Shakilaa@wit.org.uk 07458 307355

COMMUNITY PANTRIES AND FOOD COOPS

Community food pantries are membership schemes offering weekly discounted food, as well as advice and support. Eligibility differs from service to service - contact individual services for more information.

The Food Store, Limborough House, Burdett Estate, Thomas Rd, London E14 7AW. Provides subsidised food to local residents. Fridays and Saturdays. Referral only. Also doing deliveries for vulnerable residents. Contact Masoom Ahmed thefoodstoreburdett@outlook.com

Manorfield Primary School running a weekly food pantry offering subsidised food to families. if your child attends Manorfield Primary School and would like to access the Food Pantry, contact the school main reception, or e-mail admin@manorfield.towerhamlets.sch.uk

Fieldgate Mansions Community Centre, 15 Romford Street, London E1 1HX. Thursdays 10am-12pm. To become a member, you must live or work within 15 minutes of the clubs. Contact Laura.McHugh@family-action.org.uk for more details.

Cyprus Street Estate, Cyprus Street, Tower Hamlets, London, E20NW. Wednesday 2-4pm. To become a member, you must live or work within 15 minutes of the clubs. Contact Laura.McHugh@family-action.org.uk for more details.

Women's Inclusive Team, Mayfield House, 202a Cambridge Heath Road, London, E2 9LJ.

Tuesdays 12-2pm. All new members should fill in an [eligibility form](#) if possible.

Vulnerable community members can talk to the team about delivery arrangements.

WIT operates a food bank service as well. Contact Shakila Ali Shakilaa@wit.org.uk

07458 307355

St Hilda's Food Coop, 18 Club Row, London E2 7EY. Offers fresh fruit and vegetables at affordable prices to the local community. Thursdays 11am-3pm.

Contact Yolande yolande@sthildas.org.uk or Cindy foodcoop@sthildas.org.uk

MARKETS

Markets are a great source of low-cost produce, including imported culturally-appropriate fruits and vegetables. The following markets have fruit & veg stalls:

- Stroudley Walk, E3
- Whitechapel Road, E1 (plus fish)
- Watney Street, E1
- Chrisp Street, E14 (plus fish)
- Bethnal Green, E2

FOOD SUPPORT

HEALTHY START VOUCHERS

Healthy Start vouchers are going digital.

If you are more than ten weeks pregnant or have a child under four, you may be entitled to get help to buy healthy food and milk.

Visit <https://www.healthystart.nhs.uk/> to learn more and apply.

If you are already receiving Healthy Start vouchers, the way you receive this will soon change from paper voucher to prepaid card. You should have been contacted about this change already by letter or leaflet within your voucher pack.

Whether you are applying for the first time, or currently receiving paper vouchers, you must go online now to apply for your prepaid card. If your application is successful, you will typically receive your prepaid card within seven working days of your application.

Read the [FAQs](#) or more details.

[Apply now >](#)

FREE SCHOOL MEALS

All infants and primary school children in Tower Hamlets are entitled to free school meals regardless of the parent(s) income.

Nursery and secondary school children may be able to get free meals if they are in receipt of benefits.

Read the Tower Hamlets Council [information page](#) for more details.

EASTER HOLIDAY FOOD AND ACTIVITIES PROGRAMME

A range of organisations are offering free fun activities and a meal this Easter – and places are available for children in reception up to Year 11 (inclusive).

To find out more download the [Easter holidays activities programme](#).

COMMUNITY HUBS

The following organisations offer support services, including picking up shopping/ medication; a friendly phone call; weekly activity pack with word searches, crosswords; and cooking and delivering a meal:

Burdett FC - delivering medication, food and other essentials or support to high-risk or vulnerable families in the Burdett area. Contact 07930 983651

Neighbours in Poplar - contact 020 7987 0257 nip65@msn.com

St Hilda's East referral only – contact Tower Hamlets Homes Support Line for more info 020 7364 5015

HOW TO HELP

DONATE

Bow Food Bank needs funds to purchase additional food to meet growing demand caused by COVID-19. It is also accepting donations of food on Sundays 12:30 – 3:00 pm and Mondays 9:00 – 12:30 pm. See their [list of popular items](#) and keep checking their [website](#) for updates.

First Love Foundation needs donations of **non-perishable** food items and toiletries. The warehouse is open for food donations on **Tuesdays and Thursdays, 9am – 12pm and 2pm – 4pm**. [More details](#). Or [donate funds](#).

St Dunstan's Food Bank accepts food. List of [most needed items](#) on their website. [Donate funds](#) via Paypal.

Women's Inclusive Team is providing grocery shopping and hot food to Afghanistan refugees. Help them do more by [donating](#).

VOLUNTEER

[Tower Hamlets Volunteer Centre](#) has a variety of roles to support the local community.

[Women's Inclusive Team](#) are running a food delivery and community assistance service and are looking for volunteers.

Wen (Women's Environmental Network)
20 Club Row, London, E2 7EY

Edited by
Jo Wilson

[Email Jo](#) with updates or additions

POWERED BY
Wen.

Dear Ruth,

Thank you for working through what must have been a complex submission. Here's our responses. We also attach two extra documents ie the information poster and the list of food organisations that can help people with food security needs.

1 - Within your resubmission, please can you provide the poster referenced in Section C11. The committee would like to see how the shopping voucher will be advertised and also how the amount to each participant will be allocated.

Please see the pdf of the poster.

We have lots of discussions across the universities about compensation. Reading does lots of food tasting in its food labs and so has clear guidelines. We have to be careful not to coerce participation, and not to interfere with benefits and at the same time, recognise the time participants give us, and the inconvenience participating can present. On the estate we are studying, it is hard to recruit participants. Our community researchers who are from a nearby estate tell us that people are unlikely to take part unless there is something clearly in it for them. In London, we are working to the living minimum wage amount per hour, although of course, we are not 'paying participants' but reimbursing them. This means that participants in the synchronous interviews and mapping will receive £15 and the participants taking packs which have 3 possible methods will receive £15-30 depending on whether they do two or one. We are advising people to do a maximum of two methods and in fact at the live event, we will not be able to do more than one method per person. The packs and live methods cover the same kind of ground, so people can't do both. We'd be very interested in a Sussex University sharing event where researchers could talk through some of these ethical and practical issues.

2 - Please can you confirm if the services listed in Section C14 is the full list of supporting services and if not, please can you provide a full list with your resubmission.

The list of food organisations is extensive and has just updated by our partner. It shows different kind of food support and you can see the organisations on the attached pdf.

3 - Please can you add the following sentence to the Participant Information Sheet 'if you have any questions or concerns relating to this research please contact Ruth Stirton, Chair of the Social Sciences and Arts Cross Schools Research Ethics Committee (r.stirton@sussex.ac.uk)'.
'

DONE

4 - Please can you add a specific date/time by which participants can no longer request their withdrawal from the project to the Consent Form.

DONE

5 - Please can you confirm where the interviews will take place in the application and also in the Participant Information Sheet.

ADDED TO C12

These will take place in the grounds of the estate. We are setting up tables with chairs where people can learn about the methods, and volunteer to undertake one of them if they choose to. The interview tables will be placed across the estate so there is some privacy. We are also offering a walk and talk option as one of the goals is to encourage people to visit different parts of the estate like the allotments and orchard.

ADDED to Participant Info Sheet

The interview will take place on the estate at one of the tables or as a walk and talk around the orchard and grounds, depending on what you prefer.

6 - Please can you check the Participant Information Sheet for typos and clarify what UKRI is (for example, "part of a study funded by the government agency, UK Research and Innovation "UKRI").

Checked, and added UKRI info.

7 - Within the Consent Form for project participants there is no mention of future use beyond this specific project and research team. Might project data be used in the wider context of the project with other teams? If so, please can you address this within your resubmission.

The data on these studies will stay within the Sussex team. Each of the universities on the project has local studies and whilst the preliminary findings and subsequent analyses will be shared, the data won't. Moreover, because it's an inter-disciplinary team, the data generated in Sussex studies do not fit with other disciplinary approaches. So I have left as is.

Thanks very much, Elaine